

Plasmonic edge in graphene on hexagonal boron nitride flakes: AFM-in-SEM analysis of enhanced electron emission

Heterostructures of graphene and hexagonal boron nitride (G/hBN) are studied with a view to many electronic applications due to the possibility of tuning their electronic properties. Their specific properties can be revealed by AFM-in-SEM correlative microscopy which provides simultaneous acquisition of signals from both methods.

Figure 1: G/hBN flake on Si substrate a) AFM surface, b) SEM morphology in SE mode, c) height and SEM intensity profiles of the G/h-BN edge, d) 3D CPEM image focused on enhancement G/h-BN edge

Figure 2: Simultaneous acquisition of electronic and topographical information from the heterostructure.

AFM-in-SEM analysis confirms that the enhancement at the edge was caused by the localization of electrons, i.e. by localized plasmonic vibrations under visible light illumination. Thus, the combined CPEM image confirmed the electronic effect, i.e. visible frequency plasmons, behind Raman enhancement. The edge of the G/hBN heterostructure thus exhibits potential in sensing applications.

SEM-SE images of G/hBN heterostructure flakes show an enhanced signal along the edges that is attributed to localized electrons. A similar signal enhancement is also visible at the edges of the G/hBN flake in the Raman map of silicon and 2D graphene peaks (bright yellow color in Figure 3).

a) Optical image

b) Raman map in Si peak

c) Raman map in 2D peak

Figure 3: Images of G/hBN flake on Si substrate a) optical, Raman map of b) Si and c) 2D peak intensity

